

OCEAN:ICE News – September 2024

OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN:ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to September's edition of OCEAN:ICE News! We're excited to bring you the latest updates from the OCEAN:ICE community.

In this issue, you'll meet our featured researcher of the month and catch up on key activities, including the European Polar Science Week 2024, the International Symposium on Verification and Validation of Cryospheric Models, and our Climate Coffees. Don't forget to mark your calendars for the upcoming OCEAN:ICE storyline meetings, the Ocean Best Practices System Workshop VIII, and more exciting events.

We hope you enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to sharing more in October!

Researcher in the Spotlight: Elizabeth Case

We are continuing with our article series 'Researcher in the Spotlight'. Check out our latest feature on Elizabeth Case, a postdoctoral researcher at the [Institute for Marine and Atmospheric Research \(IMAU\)](#) at [Utrecht University](#).

Read the feature on Elizabeth [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN:ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN:ICE Activities

European Polar Science Week 2024

The European Polar Science community came together in Copenhagen over the 3rd to the 6th of September 2024 to discuss cutting edge science and future pathways to collaboration.

OCEAN:ICE was well represented in presentations, plenary and panel discussions. Ruth Mottram (DMI) presented the project during the well-attended opening and closing plenary discussions in the large Queens Hall in the Black Diamond, as well as giving a more detailed talk on progress in a targeted session. Other members of the project gave talks about aspects of OCEAN:ICE work, or about other projects that have strong ties to OCEAN:ICE.

We were particularly happy that several of our early career scientists were represented with Romain Millan (IGE) presenting Earth observation datasets developed in WP3 and Stina Wahlgren (UGOT) presenting exciting results from the Huginn UAV from underneath the Dotson ice shelf. Our new Ukrainian partners NASC were also represented with some early results shown by Anastasiia Chyhareva.

Read more highlights from the European Polar Science Week 2024 on our [website](#).

International Symposium on Verification and Validation of Cryospheric Models

From 4 to 9 August 2024, Northumbria University in collaboration with the International Glaciology Society organised a symposium on the Verification and Validation of Cryospheric Models. The symposium brought together over 100 scientists from a range of glaciological disciplines, to discuss the integration of observational products with the latest numerical model developments and process studies. Various members of the OCEAN:ICE consortium were part of the local organising team (Jan De Rydt, Qing Qin) and the scientific steering committee (Hilmar Gudmundsson, Ruth Mottram, Frank Pattyn).

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Upcoming Events

OCEAN:ICE Storyline Meetings

In OCEAN:ICE, we run Storyline Meetings which we use as a communication tool so that the work packages in the project can talk together across the following cross-cutting themes:

- Deep uncertainty in freshwater fluxes
- Bottom water and lower cell
- Oxygen isotope exploitation
- The role of pole(s) in the global climate system

Coming up in September the following cross-cutting theme meetings have been scheduled:

- 13 September 2024, 11:00 CEST, *The role of pole(s) in the global climate system* led by Robin Smith (UREAD)
- 13 September 2024, 15:00 CEST, *Oxygen isotope exploitation* led by Casimir de Lavergne (CNRS)
- 17 September 2024, 11:00 CEST, *Bottom water and lower cell* led by Povl Abrahamsen (BAS)

These series of Storyline Meetings contribute to OCEAN:ICE's milestones.

A banner image for OCEAN:ICE Storyline Meetings. The background is a snowy, icy landscape with a penguin in the center. The OCEAN:ICE logo is in the top left. The text 'Storyline Meetings' is in a large, bold, blue font in the center. At the bottom left is the European Union flag, and to its right is text about funding from the European Union and UK Research and Innovation.

 OCEAN:ICE

Storyline Meetings

 OCEAN:ICE is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452 and by UK Research and Innovation

Ocean Best Practices System Workshop VIII

[ObsSea4Clim](#), [TipESM](#), [ClimTip](#) and [OCEAN:ICE](#) projects are jointly going to deliver the workshop 'Ocean-Climate Nexus – Importance of Ocean Observing for Tipping Points' on the 17th of October 2024, at 17:00-18:30 CEST. Andrew Meijers (BAS) will deliver a talk on Novel Ocean Observations representing OCEAN:ICE.

Join this free online workshop by registering [here](#).

ocean best practices 2022-2030

OBPS Workshop VIII / 14-18 October, 2024 [ONLINE]
Ocean-Climate Nexus - Importance of Ocean Observing for Tipping Points, and the downstream effects of Tipping Points.
17 Oct | 15:00 - 16:30 UTC

Background images credits: Toby Matthews (Marine Eye) and Shaun Wells (Oceana Dive) / Ocean Image Bank

Climate Coffee

[Xabier Davila](#) on Tracing Freshwater Sources - Estimates from Salinity and Seawater Isotope Relationships
3 October 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CEST).

Register [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Xabier Davila
Tracing Freshwater Sources - Estimates from Salinity and Seawater Isotope Relationships
3 October 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CEST
Online

Ana Oliveira on CLIM4cities ML and AI Modelling
17 October 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CEST).
Register [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Ana Oliveira

AI for Urban Climate: An EO-Based Approach for Heatwaves Exposure and Adaptation – CLIM4cities project

17 October 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CEST
Online

Danish Meteorological Institute

CLIM4cities is under a programme of, and funded by, the European Space Agency. Views expressed do not reflect the official opinion of the European Space Agency.

[Oliver Huhn](#) on [Record of Water Mass Age and Meltwater Fractions, Weddell Sea](#)
14 November 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CEST).

Register [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Oliver Huhn

Record of water mass age and meltwater fractions, Weddell Sea

14 November 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CET
Online

Danish Meteorological Institute

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Happening Soon

OCEAN:ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 18-20 September 2024, [EPOC](#) Annual Meeting, Reading
- 23-25 September 2024, OCEAN:ICE and IAPSO Joint Event, Copenhagen & online
- 30 September - 1 October 2024, [29th International Symposium on Polar Sciences](#), Incheon
- 28-30 October 2024, [SO-CHIC](#) Annual Project Meeting, Paris & online
- 21-23 October 2024, [PolarRES](#) Annual Meeting, Potsdam

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN:ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

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www.ocean-ice.eu

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/euoceanice/>

https://twitter.com/OCEANICE_EU

<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

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Who is OCEAN:ICE?

OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN:ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

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